

Life cycle assessment of enhanced materials recovery from LTO-rich anode waste recycling via froth flotation

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ABSTRACT

The introduction of alternative anode chemistries into the market, such as lithium titanium oxide (LTO), will likely generate challenges in lithium-ion battery (LIB) recycling processes. This study provides a life cycle impact assessment (LCA) for a hydrometallurgical battery recycling process enhanced with anode material separation via flotation. Life cycle inventory (LCI) was obtained through process simulation, assuming a feed of mixed battery materials including nickel manganese cobalt (NMC), LTO, and graphite. Two scenarios were modeled in which flotation separation was placed before the hydrometallurgical flowsheet (SC1) or, alternatively, placed to treat the leach residue (SC2). For SC1, the battery elements recovery rates were: 85 % Li, 92 % Co, 89 % Ni, 87 % Mn, 89 % Cu and 88 % Ti, whereas for SC2 they were 88 % Li, 94 % Co, 94 % Ni, 90 % Mn, 97 % Cu and 96 % Ti. The LCA results for the organics in solvent extraction (SX) were for SC1 energy resource fossil (ERf) 76 %, eutrophication freshwater (ETHf) 71 % and global warming (GW) 69 %, while in SC2 were of 78 % and ETHf and GW with 70 %. Acidification (AC) was not affected considerably by the routes, as normalized results showed a difference of < 5 %. Additionally, the simulation results showed that a longer flotation time in SC1 resulted in losses of lithium metal oxides (LMeOs) to the float stream. Nevertheless, although in SC2, EIs were higher compared to SC1, higher recovery yields with minimized waste generation could be demonstrated.

1. Introduction

The European Union (EU) is developing numerous strategies and policies aiming for carbon neutrality by 2050 to all societal activities and sectors. According to the Progress on the competitiveness of clean energy technologies (European Commission, 2023) Li-ion batteries (LIBs) contribute crucially to the energy transition both in mobile and stationary applications. It was estimated that, in 2023, there were almost 14 million electronic vehicles (EV) sold globally, which is approximately 18 % of the total cars sold in 2023. Consequently, there have been numerous rapid developments in the sector to supply the battery market with the most efficient, cost-effective and sustainable LIBs technology. Along with the goal to reduce Co content in batteries by substituting it with Ni and other metals – that has led to the development of chemistries such as lithium nickel manganese cobalt oxide (NMC622, NMC811) and entirely Co-free lithium manganese oxide (LMO) and lithium-iron phosphate (LFP) (Kaushik et al., 2024) – there have also

been parallel developments related to the anode chemistry. For anodes, these developments include the move away from more conventional graphite to materials such as Li metal, and silicon, to name just a few (Hossain et al., 2023). Amongst the alternative anode options, lithium titanate oxide (LTO) batteries – in which LTO forms the anode material – have gained increasing popularity within the LIB sector due to their structural stability, operational safety, fast charging and durability (Zhang et al., 2022).

As the market for batteries has increased rapidly, the European Union has acknowledged that recycling is a priority. Recycling will play a pivotal role on early stages of the value chain, thus energy security for the 200–800 kilotons demand forecasted by 2030 (European Commission, 2023). Furthermore, with the EU battery regulation, new recycling targets in which 65 % of the average weight of LIBs must be recycled by 2025 and 70 % by 2030, have been mandated. Currently, the battery recycling industry typically aims to recover the more valuable cathode materials, such as Li, Ni, and Co, whereas the recovery of anode

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materials has often been overlooked. So that the related materials typically either ends up in the leach residue, slag, or is burned as part of the treatment process (Van Hoof et al., 2023).

There is limited information regarding of the behavior of LTO anode within the battery recycling processes in the literature (Sahivirta et al., 2024). Some studies suggest that leaching of LTO leads to TiO_2 in the leach residue (Feng et al., 2023; Waidha et al., 2023; Ali Nowroozi et al., 2022; Chigada et al., 2021). Nevertheless, previous studies investigated lithium metal oxides (LMeO) as cathode with an LTO anode. However, typically industrial black mass is composed by cathode material along with graphite, that is present in approximately from 35 % to 60 % in weight (Wilke et al., 2023). Therefore, it is likely that in the future, leach residue may be composed of a mix of graphite and TiO_2 . Consequently, these materials will need to be separated from each other to minimize waste and reduce environmental impacts (EI) of recycling processes. The importance of this issue was recently highlighted by Arellano-Sanchez et al. (2025), who suggested that further research in LTO anode recovery is required to deal with the increasing amount of LTO-rich anode black mass that maybe encountered in future battery recycling processes feeds.

Ti, and natural graphite, are considered critical raw materials (European Union, 2024). There is a high demand for Ti from aerospace, automotive, medical, and industrial applications, due to its properties of strength-to-weight ratio, corrosion resistance and biocompatibility. Recycling will be an increasingly important source for Ti in the future to help reduce pressure on the related mineral resources that are currently estimated to run out between 2100 and 2175 (Sverdrup and Sverdrup, 2023). Furthermore, there is a supply chain risk linked to graphite for battery manufacturers since over 77 % of global production comes from China (Geological Survey, 2024). The high grade (~99.95 %) required for batteries, is traditionally achieved through mining and further purification methods (Glass, et al., 2022). Thus, efficiently separating graphite from LTO becomes crucial, to make secondary sources a more attractive option. Currently, several methods for recovering graphite are available, including hydrometallurgical and mechanical processes (Natarajan & Aravindan, 2020). In addition, froth flotation is a promising method that can be scaled-up for industrial application that has been the focus of recent research on LIB recycling (Nazari et al., 2024).

Froth flotation is a mineral processing technique that exploits differences in the hydrophobicity of solid particles to enable an efficient separation/enrichment of mixed materials. It is widely used for the extraction of valuable elements present in primary raw materials and more recently, is increasingly applied as a more direct recycling method from End-of-Life (EoL) Li-ion batteries (Nazari et al., 2024). Due to the natural hydrophobicity of anodic graphite, froth flotation has proven an effective approach for carbonaceous material from mixed battery waste black mass. For example, Verdugo et al. (2022), Vanderbruggen et al. (2022), and Rinne et al. (2023), have all demonstrated the applicability of this technique using process parameters similar to those normally used for industrial graphite flotation (Vasumathi et al., 2023). More recently, Sahivirta et al. (2024) explored the use of froth flotation for the separation of emergent anode materials like LTO, highlighting the ability of this approach to separate graphite and anode materials from LTO batteries. Consequently, froth flotation studies can contribute to an improvement in evolving battery recycling processes that target a circular economy approach. Thus, this study focuses on the life cycle assessment of two potential hydrometallurgical-based battery recycling processes, where anode materials separation is enhanced by froth flotation. In this investigated approach Ni, Co, Mn, Li, and TiO_2 are recovered from the battery waste, whereas graphite, Fe, and Al were considered as inert waste with minimal environmental burden.

2. Materials and methods

An extensive literature review was carried out to obtain the parameters and chemical reactions for the process simulation. SIM module

within HSC v10.4 Metso (2024) software was used to obtain the life cycle inventory (LCI) of the battery recycling process enhanced with anode recovery. OpenLCA and Ecoinvent database 3.10 were used to obtain the life cycle impact assessment (LCIA).

2.1. Raw materials

Feed material information was obtained from the characterization by Jegan Roy et al. (2021), described in Table 1. Batteries were discharged using 20 % NaCl for 24 h and dried. The black mass was shredded, and plastic impurities were removed manually and crushed. Additionally, the binder and electrolyte were removed from the sample by drying at ~60 °C overnight. For the simulations, full removal of PVDF binder was assumed.

2.2. Process description

The recycling process investigated is described in detail within the supplementary information (SI). The flowsheet was simulated using SIM module within HSC© Metso (2024) software version 10.4. Hydro and Particles models within SIM module were used for the simulation. The flowsheet and system boundary are depicted in Fig. 1.

Two flotation units were designed to complement the hydrometallurgical battery recycling process simulations. The feed for the battery recycling flowsheet was 7000 metric tonnes (mt) of black mass treated per year (Velázquez-Martínez et al., 2019), based on the black mass composition outlined in Table 1. It is estimated that 1 kg of black mass from EVs is approximately equivalent to 3–4 kg of battery cells (Rinne et al., 2024; Green Transport Delta, 2025).

- (1) The first scenario (SC1) represents a process where the LTO-rich black mass is fed to flotation cell prior hydrometallurgical processing. Following flotation of 3 min duration, the graphite and lithium metal oxides (LMeOs) are separated. Graphite is concentrated in the froth phase (*i.e.* float), whereas (LMeOs) reports to the sink. The graphite concentrate is dried by thickening and filtration. The sink fraction is further treated by hydrometallurgical means to recover Li, Co, Ni, and Mn while TiO_2 is obtained as the leach residue.
- (2) In the second scenario (SC2), LTO-rich black mass is fed to the hydrometallurgical process in which Li, Mn, Co, and Ni are recovered. After leaching, TiO_2 and graphite remain in the leach residue. The leach residue is further treated by froth flotation to separate the TiO_2 and graphite. After 3 min of flotation, graphite reports to the float concentrate, while TiO_2 remains in the sink. Both fractions – float and sink – undergo thickening and filtering respectively, to remove as much excess water as possible.

Consequently, further treatment is needed to obtain a higher purity of TiO_2 under both scenarios. Nevertheless, such possible treatment is outside the scope of this current research, as in literature there are many processes in which TiO_2 undergoes pyrometallurgical treatment to synthesize materials like $\text{Li}_4\text{Ti}_5\text{O}_{12}$ or Li_2TiO_3 and where the graphite reporting to the TiO_2 sink could be used as a reductant or consumed within the oxidizing environment (Zhang et al., 2011; Feng et al., 2023). The data for the process simulation of flotation was obtained from the study of Sahivirta et al. (2024), in which NMC811 was floated with graphite and LTO material, which resulted in the LMOs in the sink, whereas graphite went to the float. Additionally, flotation parameters required for Cu, Al and Fe were obtained from Ruismäki et al. (2020) for SC1, indicating, approximately 92 % of these elements transfer to the sink along with the LMeOs. In both cases there was no report of binder being present in the material during the experiments. It must be highlighted that the kinetic data obtained from Sahivirta et al. (2024) was obtained with fully liberated model black mass, whose behavior may deviate from industrially produced black mass. For this study, it is

Table 1
Composition of black mass used as feed in the recycling process simulation (SC1 and SC2).

Component	LiNiO ₂	LiMnO ₂	LiCoO ₂	Li ₄ Ti ₅ O ₁₂	Cu	Al	Fe	Graphite
wt%	30.71	11.33	11.81	20.86	2.82	0.62	0.97	20.85

Fig. 1. System boundary flowsheet for the assessment with possible scenarios and system expansion highlighted for the battery recycling process.

assumed that the binder had been completely removed during the pre-treatment stage, therefore behavior may potentially deviate from that of industrially produced black mass. As observed by Vanderbruggen et al. (2022), Farrokhpay et al. (2021), and Wang et al. (2015), the presence of PVDF binder in the cathode increases hydrophobicity, thus affects the related process kinetics. Nonetheless, it serves as a good estimation since, to the best of the authors' knowledge, there is currently no information available related to the froth flotation kinetics of industrial LTO-rich black mass.

2.3. LCA scope

2.3.1. Goal and scope

The goal of the study is to compare through life cycle assessment (LCA) the environmental impacts of the two flowsheets designed within SIM to recover anode material from the LTO-rich anodes in the waste feed of the battery recycling process following ISO standards 14040:2006 (ISO 14040, 2006) and 14044:2006 (ISO 14044, 2006). The assessment was conducted utilizing OpenLCA 2.0 by GreenDelta (GreenDelta, 2024) with Ecoinvent database 3.10 (Ecoinvent v3.10, 2024). The functional unit selected for this study is 1 kg of treated black mass. The scope of the study was to recover cathode material: Li, Co, Ni, and Mn through hydrometallurgical methods and anode material through flotation. The system boundary is illustrated in Fig. 1. The location boundary of the study was defined as Europe, wherever possible. An avoided burden/system expansion approach was applied to

do a (1:1) substitution of recycled materials against the mining of the raw materials to avoid allocation. Data sensitivity was addressed through investigation of the impact of flotation time changes in SC1. Moreover, process sensitivity was addressed by variation of the black mass composition in which the NMC811 (50/50) ratio feed was replaced by NMC111 and NMC622 in SC2.

2.3.2. Inventory analysis

Life cycle inventory was obtained through process simulation utilizing SIM module of HSC software by Metso. Currently, solvent extraction (SX) chemicals are not found within the Ecoinvent 3.10 database. Therefore, Cyanex 272 and D2EPPA were modeled according to Cao et al. (2023), in which only 5% (Cheng et al., 2011) of the circulated organics are considered for the LCI, an approach also previously utilized by Rinne et al. (2024). Methyl isobutyl carbinol (MIBC), ((CH₃)₂CHCH₂CH(OH)CH₃) consumption described by Sahivirta et al. (2024) of 8 ppm within the flotation cell was not simulated as a result of limitations related to the control of solutions for the particle module within the SIM software. Due to the minimal consumption (8 ppm) and that simulation was not viable for methyl isobutyl carbinol (MIBC), ((CH₃)₂CHCH₂CH(OH)CH₃), it was excluded from the LCI. The results obtained from the simulation are as follows in Table 2:

2.3.3. Impact Assessments methods & Indicators

The impact method to generate the life cycle inventory analysis (LCIA), background data for the analysis was obtained through

Table 2

Depicts the first scenario (SC1) and second Scenario (SC2) process data obtained by simulation.

Input	SC1	SC2	unit
Black mass	1.00	1.00	kg
Electricity	1.30	1.43	MJ
Heat, steam	3.25	4.27	MJ
Water	9.71	8.89	kg
Sulfuric acid	2.41	2.70	kg
Hydrogen peroxide	294.62	347.78	g
Caustic soda/sodium hydroxide	1.37	1.57	kg
Lime/quicklime	10.99	14.29	g
Sodium carbonate/soda ash	333.52	344.41	g
Iron scrap	22.26	23.91	g
Manganese sulfate	7.81	9.63	g
Cobalt sulfate	7.69	8.45	g
Nickel sulfate	56.82	66.10	g
Sulfur dioxide, liquid	6.81	7.02	g
Oxygen, liquid	63.94	66.27	g
Cyanex 272	0.12	0.14	kg
D2EHPA	0.26	0.30	kg
C ₁₂ H ₂₆ (Kerosene)	0.40	0.67	kg
Outputs	SC1	SC2	unit
Lithium carbonate	236.31	244.09	g
Cobalt sulfate	326.56	333.44	g
Nickel sulfate	808.44	858.53	g
Manganese dioxide	129.75	132.51	g
Leach residue	N/A	N/A	
Neutral waste	0.14	0.16	kg
Sodium sulfate	3.18	3.59	kg
Wastewater	6.36	5.60	kg
Oxygen gas	0.21	0.24	kg
Water vapour	3.13	3.33	kg
Hydrogen	0.97	1.05	g
Copper	25.33	27.21	g
TiO ₂	154.77	153.552	g

Ecoinvent 3.10 database and ReCiPe 2016 (Huijbregts et al., 2017) midpoint with hierarchy perspective was selected for the assessment. The selected impact categories for this assessment were selected according to Santero and Hendry (2016), recommendations for mining industry: global warming (GW, measured in kg CO₂-eq.), terrestrial acidification (AC, kg SO₂-eq.), Eutrophication: freshwater (EThf, kg P-eq.), Photochemical oxidant formation: human health (POFh, kg NO_x-Eq), and ozone depletion potential (ODP, kg CFC-11-eq.). Ecotoxicity, freshwater (Exf, kg 1,4-DCB-Eq), Particulate matter formation (PM, kg PM_{2.5}-Eq) and Human toxicity: carcinogenic (HTc, kg 1,4-DCB-Eq), were studied to have information about toxicity. Additionally, Energy resources: non-renewable, fossil (Erf, kg oil-Eq), were assessed to understand the burden of the energy supplied to the background processes.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Processing and impact results

Firstly, the recovery rates and their variations in different flowsheet scenarios were studied. For SC1, the battery element recovery rates were: 85 % Li, 92 % Co, 89 % Ni, 87 % Mn, 89 % Cu and 88 % Ti,

Table 3

LCA results by impact category of SC1 and SC2.

Impact category	Unit	SC1	SC2
Energy resources: non-renewable, fossil (Erf)	kg oil-Eq	4.38	5.31
Eutrophication: freshwater (EThf)	kg P-Eq	5.75 x10 ⁻³	6.62x10 ⁻³
Global warming (GW)	kg CO ₂ -Eq	11.79	13.82
Photochemical oxidant formation: human health (POFh)	kg NO _x -Eq	2.17 x10 ⁻²	2.55 x10 ⁻²
Human toxicity: carcinogenic (HTc)	kg 1,4-DCB-Eq	2	2.32
Particulate matter formation (PM)	kg PM _{2.5} -Eq	1.99 x10 ⁻²	2.28 x10 ⁻²
Ozone depletion (ODP)	kg CFC-11-Eq	3.15 x10 ⁻⁶	3.6 x10 ⁻⁶
Acidification: terrestrial (AC)	kg SO ₂ -Eq	0.06	0.06
Ecotoxicity: freshwater (Exf)	kg 1,4-DCB-Eq	0.57	0.66

Fig. 2. Comparison of recycling impacts of SC1 and SC2 to virgin materials (normalized results).

whereas for SC2 were 88 % Li, 94 % Co, 94 % Ni, 90 % Mn, 97 % Cu and 96 % Ti. The LCA results for SC1 and SC2 are shown in Table 3 and are presented in Fig. 2 where the system is expanded according to the materials recovered of every scenario for an adequate comparison with the virgin material production, maintaining the yields mentioned above for every scenario. It was observed that the biggest difference in environmental impacts between SC1 and SC2 is in Erf at approximately 20 % and the lowest of Exf of ~ 3 %, Fig. 2. However, AC, Exf, ODP and PM were under the 50 % of environmental impacts contributions when compared to the environmental impacts of virgin materials production via mining. For GW SC1 was 12 % lower than SC2, for SC2 the GW were + 3 % to the mining of the virgin materials. Additionally, for SC1 only Erf goes over the environmental impacts by 23 % of the production of virgin materials while for SC2, only Erf and EThf goes over the EI of virgin materials with 44 % and 11 % respectively. Additionally, for HTc and POFh environmental impacts are at least under 25 % of the EI of the production of virgin materials for both scenarios. The higher environmental impacts associated to SC2 could be the result of higher recovery of Li, Mn, Co, Ni and Ti, as in this case, the flotation is placed after leaching. As more LMeOs reach the hydrometallurgy separation and recovery stages, more raw materials needed (acid, peroxide hydroxide, and organics). Hence, the use of these chemicals increments the burden for the environmental impacts. Nevertheless, SC2 recovers higher yield than SC1 therefore less material is lost to the float. Therefore, flotation could be in this case SC2 a waste treatment to recover valuable material from leach residue.

Fig. 3. Calculated environmental impacts of the recycling flowsheet, SC1 and SC2, divided by a) and b) stream and by c) and d) activity within the recycling flowsheet (dominance analysis). Ancillary activities include electricity, water, steam, and wastewater neutralization. Percent is calculated within the levels of EI.

3.2. Dominance analysis

The LCA of SC1 are shown in Fig. 3 (a and c) by dominance analysis – where the stages are ranked according to the activities relative shares – Fig. 3a represents the results by stream and Fig. 3b is the total impact by activity within the recycling flowsheet, ancillary activities composed of water supply, steam, neutralization, and electricity. The results suggest that more significant environmental impacts come from the usage of organics specially ERf with 76 %, ETH 71 % and GW 69 % observed, Fig. 3a. The organics are used within the solvent extraction operations (SX) for the separation of Ni, Mn, and Co that will be consequently recovered as metal salt with high purity. Another activity with important EI contributions was leaching with 30 % AC and 25 % PM observed in Fig. 3c. These contributions are associated with the use of sulfuric acid, as corroborated by Fig. 3a and it is worth noting that sulfuric acid is also used in the SX operations. Furthermore, it was noted that the environmental impacts associated with the usage of NaOH were ~ 20 % for ODP and Exf (Fig. 2a) – the recycling processes utilize NaOH as a pH regulator.

SC2 LCA results are also displayed in Fig. 3 (b and d) the dominance analysis by flow corresponds to Fig. 3b and Fig. 3d dominance analysis is shown by activity. As well as in SC1 ancillary activities are formed by water supply, steam, neutralization, and electricity. In SC2 it was also observed (Fig. 3b) that most of the EI contributions are related to the use of organics specially ERf with the major contribution of 78 %, GW and ETHf both with 70 % and the minor EI contributions of PM with 38 % and Exf with 40 %. Like SC1, SC2 uses the organics for SX processes. The results confirm the dominance of the organics (used in Ni, Co, and Mn separation) on environmental impacts, Fig. 3d. It was observed in the dominance analysis that the investigated recycling process in both scenarios is not heavily dependent on energy, Fig. 3 (a, b). Consequently, the environmental impact associated with energy sources should remain

applicable despite future changes in the energy mix. The renewable energy sources (RES) market will be varying constantly as the EU reaches its goal of carbon neutrality by 2050 (European Commission, 2020).

Overall, the dominance analysis results reveal that the EI contributions associated with the use of organics in the battery recycling flowsheet are overwhelming for both scenarios. In addition, it is observed that ERf and GW are two of the highest impact categories, suggesting that further research in the upstream activities using energy mix higher in renewable energy sources RES must be conducted. Therefore, this assessment identified hotspots and provided information on whether ERf and GW categories can be significantly decreased by affecting the upstream activities (organic manufacturing). Moreover, future battery recycling processes must ensure the optimal recirculation and minimal degradation and losses of the organics during the lifetime of the operations to reduce environmental impacts.

3.3. Sensitivity and uncertainty contribution analysis

The flotation time played an important role in the recovery rates of the valuable materials from the spent battery waste. It was observed during the simulation that as the flotation time increased, more LMeOs were transferred to the float concentrate, reducing the final yields, therefore, fewer materials reached the subsequent purification stages within the hydrometallurgy flowsheet. This behavior is associated with the hydrophobicity of the LMeOs, as previously reported by Vanderbruggen et al. (2021). Additionally, entrainment of LMeOs with graphite also occurs, and during extended flotation, this enhances the recovery of LMeOs into the froth phase. However, a short flotation time allows separation between LMeOs and graphite since the flotation kinetics of the latter are considerably faster. Therefore, within the simulation, flotation time was selected as 3 min to minimize the LMeOs loses to the

float concentrate, while conserving most LMeOs for further treatment within the hydrometallurgy flowsheet (Nelson et al., 2009). Nevertheless, because there is not currently any industrial facility that includes flotation for anode recovery, and no reference for the time selected is specified for graphite, uncertainty arises from the flotation time selected. Therefore, a sensitive analysis was conducted in SC1 that compares only operation conditions within the process to provide information on how the flotation time affects the results when flotation times of 4 min and 5 min are selected for the assessment. The results presented in Fig. 4a show that the impacts decreased in direct proportion to the increased flotation time. Increasing the residence time in flotation decreased the consumption of chemicals and energy in the recycling process due to a lower volume of treated material but also resulted in cathode metal losses that decreased the recycling credits. The decreased consumption of chemicals outweighed the lower credits at the observed times (3–5 min), but it is likely that the credits associated with losses would be more significant at a certain point. For instance, there were observed substantial changes in the credits at 4 and 5 min. Nevertheless, some categories (i.e., eutrophication) change was so marked that it was not possible to represent in a figure.

The feed composition (Table 1) was modified to evaluate whether the composition of the materials entering the flowsheet would result in changes in the EI. This approach has been previously undertaken by Rinne et al. (2024), and the analysis allowed to assess the sensitivity of the LCI flows hence, the impacts to the inputs. The 50 % of the feed composed by NMC811 was replaced in SC2 with the most common NMC chemistries within the EV market. The molar ratios of the LMeOs: LiCoO₂, LiNiO₂, and LiMnO₂ were altered to match NMC111 and NMC622 instead of NMC811, so the impurities were kept constant. The calculations included the relative % change in credits for every scenario. It was demonstrated (Fig. 4b) that the changes in the molar compositions did not affect the results of the EI in the model since the major change was +/-5%.

Even though the composition of the black mass is a source of uncertainty for the model, in view of the model being insensitive to the change of black mass composition, the uncertainty of the black mass will not contribute to the environmental impact results. Hence, any future improved availability of input data will provide no obvious enhancement to the robustness of the environmental impact results. Moreover, in industrial-scale battery recycling processes, it is not feasible to use design parameters for a single input feed since PLS composition is not static as it is input material dependent (Porvali et al., 2023). It is worth nothing that, this applies to black mass containing NMC material, as the

recycling system is not tailored for black mass containing LFP cathode material. During leaching, LFP cathodes could reduce power through Fe, possibly increasing Li recovery. Unfortunately, it would be expected that Fe and phosphates would be lost to the leach residue (Rinne et al., 2024). Additionally, it must be highlighted that SX parameters were obtained from Liu et al. (2019), experiments which were carried out with a mix of Ni-metal hydride batteries and LCoO₂-rich black mass and process simulation estimation. Thus, SX parameters need proper laboratory adjustment for every scenario simulated that would allow a more efficient use of organics and therefore more reliable results. Overall, the analysis suggests that the changes in the molar composition of the 50 % feed associated with NMC811/graphite for SC2 do not contribute to the uncertainty of the model. Nevertheless, the flotation time in SC1 is a “significant issue” improving proper flotation time data from pilot plant testing would provide the most significant benefits to the certainty of the results for the model. The difficulty in LCA practice is to identify and quantify input parameter correlations, which may be numerous and not typically provided in LCI databases. The importance of sensitivity and uncertainty is to identify and if possible, quantify the uncertainty to improve the robustness of its conclusions (Hauschild et al., 2018).

3.4. Limitations

The process simulation for this study focused on emerging hydrometallurgy methods to recover battery materials contained in discarded batteries, enhanced with froth flotation. Therefore, mechanical pre-treatment such as dismantling, crushing, and sieving were deemed to be outside the scope of the simulation and LCIA. The data used for the feed described as NMC-based in the study of Jegan Roy et al. (2021), was stoichiometrically adjusted to match the mass percentage of the LCO, LNO and LMO to NMC811 composition. Al, Cu and Fe content within LTO black mass was assumed to match NMC material due to data gaps related to LTO black mass characterization. Moreover, the effects associated with the presence of binder and electrolyte within black mass were also excluded from this study, since there is intensive research being conducted addressing the removal of such components from industrial black mass (Golmohammadzadeh et al., 2023).

Continuous operations might lead to higher efficiencies, that could affect retention times thereby resulting in variations within the concentrations of the final PLS. Data utilized for the SX circuit for Ni and Co is based on experiments with NMC111 black mass, thus, data quality for CoSO₄ and NiSO₄ might be affected. Additionally, the data obtained for the process simulation was determined from the literature

Fig. 4. Calculated environmental impacts for the uncertainty analysis related to a) flotation time and b) material fed into the system.

reviews—which typically consisted of laboratory batch experiments—thus is not wholly representative of industrial battery recycling processes, which increases the level of uncertainty of the results obtained from the process simulation (Table 2).

Corresponding safety information related to $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ and $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ (Sigma-Aldrich, 2023; Sigma Aldrich, 2023) indicated that such materials could be classified as non-hazardous wastes. Nevertheless, further laboratory validation is needed to corroborate this classification as their properties as waste might differ from the ones described in their respective safety data sheets (SDS). The high purity (~98 %) at which sodium sulfate ($\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$) is recovered within the flowsheet could provide opportunities for further upcycling. Therefore, ($\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$) was allocated as inert hazardous waste, along with $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ and $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$. This classification represents the minimal burden for the total environmental impacts of the battery recycling process. Effluents from every unit operation were subject to a neutralization step, which was simulated within the flowsheet. Nevertheless, according to SIM outputs the effluents from the wastewater treatment plant were approximately 4.2 g/L SO_4^{2-} , 0.01 g/L of Co^{+2} , 0.01 g/L Ni^{+2} , 0.01 g/L Mn^{+2} , and 0.2 g/L Li^+ . So, further wastewater treatment will be needed for the complete neutralization of all effluents, which is out of the scope of this study. MIBC was excluded from the LCI since at the time of the process simulation solutions could not be modeled within the mineral processing module. However, due to the minimal amount of 8 ppm found earlier by Sahivirta et al (2024), the environmental burden is expected to be negligible.

As discussed previously, flotation time is a source of uncertainty for the LCIA results, nonetheless, uncertainty has been approached with a sensitivity analysis (See section 3.4). Despite the LCIA uncertainty of the above-mentioned reasons, this study provides a justifiable approach related to the emerging methods in industrial battery recycling processes improved by flotation. Although no overlap with previous LCIA results from previous studies—due to variations in flowsheets, material fed, materials recovered and LCA boundary—this study is consistent with previous LCA/LCI process modeling with similar focus. To enhance robustness in the uncertainty of the results, it is suggested that further improvement in data quality could be addressed with experiments related to flotation time with industrial black mass. Additionally, sensitivity analysis of RES upstream manufacturing activities related to the production of organics involved in SX and expanding the boundary to include TiO_2 pyrometallurgy routes for further purification.

4. Conclusions

A hydrometallurgy battery recycling flowsheet improved with two distinct flotation scenarios was simulated to study anode recovery from recent commercialized LTO battery material (NMC111/LTO) and (NMC811/graphite). The results indicated that in SC1, recovery rates were: 85 % Li, 92 % Co, 89 % Ni, 87 % Mn, 89 % Cu and 88 % Ti. It was observed that the losses of LMeOs to float, were directly proportional to longer flotation times – behavior that might be associated to the LMeOs hydrophobicity and entrainment. Consequently, it was decided to use a short flotation time that still allows separation between LMeOs and graphite since the graphite kinetics is considerably faster than those related to LMeOs. However, further researched must be conducted to determine a proper flotation time at pilot plant scale.

Additionally, it was observed that for SC2, no losses of LMeOs were encountered for this scenario. In this case, the flotation cell was merely handling the leach residue allowing TiO_2 and graphite separation. The recovery rates for SC2 were 88 % Li, 94 % Co, 94 % Ni, 90 % Mn, 97 % Cu and 96 % Ti. This scenario confirms the hypothesis that improving a battery recycling flowsheet with flotation allows the maximum recovery of materials while minimizing waste. Currently, as no anode recovery is typically conducted in industrial battery recycling processes, this study highlights the importance of future adjustments that battery recycling flowsheets may need for handling alternative anode materials like LTO.

A LCIA was conducted – utilizing the LCI that was obtained from the flowsheet simulation – to evaluate the environmental impacts related to the two battery recycling process routes modeled. The LCA identified that acidification (AC) was not sensitive to the routes, as normalized results (Fig. 2) showed a difference of < 5 % for both scenarios. Additionally, it was identified that environmental impacts related to the use of D2EHPA and Cyanex 272 organics in the SX steps to recover Mn, Co and Ni are overwhelming in both scenarios, giving rise to contributions of ERF with 76 %, ETh with 71 % and GW with 69 % for SC1, whereas for SC2 the contribution was 78 % EThf and 70 % GW. Nevertheless, the assumption of 5 % for the total organic circulation and dividing the value for the functional unit might be an overestimation within the LCI due to the nature of the SX simulation benchmark. Dominance analysis (Fig. 3a and Fig. 3b) outlines that organics can potentially contribute between 40 % to 80 % of the total environmental burden of the battery recycling system for both SC1 and SC2. Hence, the battery recycling system is sensitive to the amount of organic solvent used for SX. It would be expected that the decrease in organic consumption within the recycling system would decrease the environmental impacts overall. Primary data from extractant manufacturers must be obtained to verify the results, especially the ones related to CO_2 -Eq generation and fossil fuel utilization. As the GW and ERF impact categories were observed to be the highest in the dominance analysis. RES utilization could decrease the environmental impacts associated to SX operations. It is worth nothing that the parameters utilized for the SX simulation were obtained from laboratory scale experiments.

A sensitivity analysis was conducted that varied the flotation time for SC1 between 3 to 5 min. The results indicated that the EI associated to the recycling processes decreased for every category as the flotation time increased. Nevertheless, the credits for the recycling process also decrease due to a reduction in final yields when flotation time is extended. In addition, feed composition was altered from Table 1 to replace the NMC111 content to match NMC622 and NMC 811 to evaluate whether the change of composition would affect the environmental impact results. The result of the assessment suggests that no significant changes were observed in the LCIA. Moreover, it was determined that further research related to solvent extraction with NMC811 – addressing experimental work as well as further LCA research – would provide the greatest benefits for the results certainty. The investigation suggests that maintaining higher yields while accounting for higher credits SC2 is the optimal option to improve the hydrometallurgy flowsheet.

Additional investigation is required to confirm the interaction at the leaching stage between NMC, graphite, and LTO. Further research is needed as the model reaches the EU battery regulation targets for 2027 (50 % Li, 90 % Co, and Ni), but falls short for the Ni target set for 2031 (95 %) (European Parliament, 2023). It is worth noting that the simulated data should be validated with pilot plant scale tests to ensure the certainty of the model's final yields. Lower final yields would result in the need for further purification stages and, therefore, reduced environmental benefits. Furthermore, although there are data gaps, special considerations and uncertainty associated with the simulation and LCIA model, this study resembles a real approximation of an industrial battery recycling process. Overall, this study highlights the challenges that the battery recycling industry might face in the future when batteries with unconventional anodes reach their end-of-life.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Diana Arellano: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Marja Rinne:** Writing – original draft, Supervision, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Luis Arturo Gomez-Moreno:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Benjamin P. Wilson:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Rodrigo Serna-Guerrero:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration. **Mari**

Lundström: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mineng.2025.109271>.

Supporting information: Detailed process descriptions, flowsheets, simulation design parameters can be found in the online version (PDF).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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